

ADMINISTRATIVE COMPETENCE OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS: ITS IMPACT TO TEACHERS' MOTIVATION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 4

Pages: 408-419

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2271

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13375387

Manuscript Accepted: 07-23-2024

Administrative Competence of School Principals: Its Impact to Teachers' Motivation

Irene T. Jose,* Maedel Joy V. Escote

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study explored the impact of principals' administrative competence on teachers' motivation in public schools in Davao de Oro. Using a quantitative research design, the study collected data from a sample of public-school teachers to assess their perceptions of their principals' administrative competence and their own motivation levels. The findings revealed a significant positive correlation between principals' administrative competence and teachers' motivation, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The results underscored the importance of effective administrative practices in enhancing teacher motivation, suggesting that principals who demonstrate strong administrative skills can significantly boost teacher morale and engagement. These findings are consistent with existing literature emphasizing the role of supportive and competent leadership in fostering a positive educational environment. The study recommends that educational institutions invest in professional development for school administrators to sustain and enhance teacher motivation and overall school performance.

Keywords: *administrative competence, teachers' motivation, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation*

Introduction

Administrative Competence refers to the ability to effectively lead and manage the administrative aspects of a school, encompassing skills and knowledge in organizational management, resource allocation, personnel management, decision-making, and strategic planning. However, when principals lack these competencies, it can lead to several issues that negatively impact teachers' motivation. Teachers with high motivation can teach the students in an effective and efficient manner, but there are lots of discrepancies and discriminations in the teaching profession that affects their motivation (Khan et al., 2018). These deficiencies can significantly demotivate teachers, leading to frustration, burnout, and hindering their overall effectiveness in the classroom.

Maintaining high levels of motivation among teachers has been a global challenge in the education sector. Research has identified various factors that can undermine teachers' motivation, leading to potential negative consequences for student learning outcomes and overall school performance. Hamdani et al (2018) emphasized the impact of principals' administrative competence on teachers' motivation through their study in Indonesia. Their findings suggested that when principals lack adequate administrative competence, teachers' performance is negatively affected. This can lead to lower levels of work motivation among teachers, which can increase their risk of burnout and diminish job satisfaction. Conversely, principals with strong administrative competence are more likely to foster an environment that promotes teachers' work motivation, leading to higher performance and productivity.

In the Philippine educational landscape, maintaining high levels of teacher motivation has been identified as a crucial challenge that can significantly influence educational outcomes. While studies have shown that teachers generally report high levels of motivation driven by factors such as existence needs, relatedness, and growth needs (Comighud, 2021). One such factor that has garnered attention is the administrative competencies of school administrators. Dalanon et al. (2018) found in his study in Cebu that despite a positive organizational climate and high teacher performance ratings, the management competencies of the school administrators were rated as only at a basic proficiency level. This finding aligns with the observations made by Kilag et al. (2023), who highlighted the critical role of effective supervision by principals and the creation of a supportive work environment in fostering high-quality teacher performance. These insights underscore the importance of administrative skills in cultivating an environment that not only maintains but also translates teacher motivation into tangible improvements in educational outcomes.

In the local context, preliminary observations of the researcher in Bayabas National High School have revealed issues related to teacher motivation. These issues seem to be linked to perceived deficiencies in the administrative competencies of the school administrators. Some of teachers have expressed feelings of demotivation, lack of administrative support that can lead to disengagement, clear guidance, and effective leadership from the admin. This lack of motivation is partly attributed to the principals' perceived inability to set specific goals, provide adequate supervision, and foster a positive and motivating work environment that create a conducive atmosphere that help everyone to develop professionally and personally through effective administrative practices.

This study aims to fill a research gap by examining the impact of principals' administrative competencies on teacher motivation in Davao de Oro. The findings could inform educational policies and practices in the region, providing insights for the development of targeted training for school principals and strategies to improve teacher motivation. Given the challenges observed, this research is urgently needed and could lead to positive changes in the region's educational landscape.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the significance of the Administrative Competence to the Public-School Teacher's Motivation in Davao De Oro. Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of Administrative Competence of School Principal as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. personal skills;
 - 1.2. administrative skills; and
 - 1.3. administrative creativity skills?
2. What is the level of Motivation of Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro in terms of:
 - 2.1. intrinsic motivation; and
 - 2.2. extrinsic motivation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between Administrative Competence and Teacher's Motivation in Public-School of Davao De Oro?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, non-experimental, descriptive correlational research approach. This approach is chosen for its ability to describe the quantitative data that collected, specifically the levels of two variables: Administrative Competence and Teacher's Motivation within the Division of Davao de Oro. The primary aim is to test the significant relationship between these variables.

A correlational study, as defined by Privitera (2020), "is a type of non-experimental research that involves measuring two or more variables and assessing the statistical relationship between them without any intervention or manipulation by the researcher". Descriptive research, according to Muijs (2020), "aims to accurately portray the characteristics of persons, situations, or groups, and the frequency with which certain phenomena occur".

Respondents

The respondents of this study were teachers from various public schools in Davao de Oro. These schools include Nabunturan Central Elementary School SPED Center, Nabunturan National Comprehensive High School and Lorenzo S. Sarmiento Sr. National High School.

These teachers were selected as they are directly involved in the educational process and their experiences and perspectives are crucial for understanding the relationship between Administrative Competence and Teacher's Motivation. Their participation provided valuable insights into the current situation and potential improvements in the educational system of Davao de Oro. The selection of teachers from different schools ensures a diverse range of responses, contributing to the robustness and validity of the study's findings.

A stratified proportionate sampling method was used in selecting participant to ensure that each subgroup within a population is represented proportionally in the sample

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Name Of Schools	Number Of Teachers Per School	Number Of Sample Per School	%
Nabunturan Central Elementary School SPED Center	76	42	24
Nabunturan National Comprehensive High School	167	93	53
Lorenzo S. Sarmiento Sr. National High School	71	39	23
Total	314	174	110%

Instrument

To comprehensively evaluate the relationship between Administrative Competence and Teachers' Motivation, this study employed two adapted research instruments. To measure the Administrative Competence of school administrators, this study adopted the research instrument developed by Sameh Abdalraof Mahmoud Yossef and Ahmed Hassan Hassan Rakha in their study titled "Efficiency of Personal and Administrative Skills for Managerial Leadership on Administrative Creativity at Najran University." This instrument comprises a total of 30 questions divided into three distinct indicators: Personal Skills (10 questions), Administrative Skills (10 questions), and Administrative Creativity Skills (10 questions). The Personal Skills indicator evaluates the inherent traits and interpersonal abilities of the administrators, while the Administrative Skills indicator assesses their proficiency in planning, organizing, and managing administrative tasks. The Administrative Creativity Skills indicator measures the administrators' capacity for innovative thinking and implementing novel approaches within their educational institutions.

By adopting this comprehensive and well-structured instrument, the study aimed to accurately gauge the various facets of Administrative Competence and their potential impact on teachers' motivation.

The second instrument, tailored to measure Teachers' Motivation, was adapted from Ramzan and Khurram (2023), this questionnaire seeks to delve into the intricacies of what motivates educators in their professional environment. Building upon the robust framework of Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, which distinguishes between intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors, this adapted version of the Teachers' Motivation Questionnaire (TMQ) aims to capture the nuanced driving forces that propel teachers towards excellence and

fulfillment in their roles. This instrument incorporates a comprehensive set of items designed to capture the intrinsic and extrinsic factors that influence teachers' desire, enthusiasm, and commitment to their professional roles. By employing these rigorously validated and contextually relevant instruments, the study aims to generate accurate and insightful data, enabling a robust analysis of the intricate interplay between Administrative Competence and Teachers' Motivation.

Procedure

This research adhered strictly to the ethical protocols and standards established by the Assumption College of Nabunturan Review Committee. The researcher meticulously sought and obtained the requisite permissions to undertake this research from key school authorities.

Acquiring Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher drafted letters soliciting permission to carry out the study, addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao de Oro, Public Schools District Supervisor and the principals of the participating secondary and elementary schools in the area. Upon receiving affirmation and approval from the relevant authorities, the researcher proceeded to obtain informed consent from the identified teacher respondents.

Obtaining Informed Consent. Prior to administering the questionnaires, the researcher ensured that all teacher respondents were provided informed consent. This process involved elucidating the purpose and nature of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the measures in place to safeguard the teachers' privacy and confidentiality. The teachers were given the opportunity to pose questions and address any concerns they might have. Only after obtaining signed informed consent forms from the teachers were questionnaires administered.

Administering the Questionnaires. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the identified teachers. This was done in coordination with the school administration. Comprehensive explanations of the questionnaire items was provided to ensure thorough understanding, and the teachers were allotted ample time to complete the questionnaires.

Data Collection. After the teachers have completed the questionnaires, the researcher gathered and encoded all the data to have a digital copy and easy storage. The complete data set was submitted to a statistician for statistical computation and analysis.

Subsequently, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the results for discussion and reporting in the study.

Data Analysis

Weighted Mean: This measure is computed by multiplying the weight (or probability) associated with a specific event or outcome by its corresponding quantitative outcome, and then summing all these products. In this context, it was used to ascertain the levels of Administrative Competence and Teachers' Motivation.

Pearson's r: Also known as the Pearson correlation coefficient, this statistical measure quantifies the strength and direction of association between two variables. In this study, it was utilized to determine the significant relationship between Administrative Competence and Teachers' Motivation in Davao de Oro.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Administrative Competence of School Principal as perceived by Public School Teachers

The level of Administrative Competence as perceived by Public School Teachers was evaluated with their corresponding indicators; Personal Skills, Administrative Skills and Administrative Creativity Skills.

Personal Skills. Table 3 shows the level of Administrative Competence as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of Personal Skills.

Table 3. *Level of Administrative Competence in terms of Personal Skills*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Enjoys and has the skill in debate and dialogue.	3.7	Agree
2. Has the ability to influence and persuade others.	3.6	Agree
3. Is fully conversant with regulations and laws concerning work.	3.7	Agree
4. Enjoys the visibility and ability to devise new things.	3.6	Agree
5. Has the ability to quickly act and make decisions in critical situations	3.7	Agree
6. Keeps implementing new ideas.	3.7	Agree
7. Gives opportunities for talented individuals.	3.6	Agree
8. Tries to create the right atmosphere for workflow.	3.6	Agree
9. Listens to the views and suggestions of teachers even if they are contrary to their own views.	3.5	Agree
10. Makes important decisions and takes responsibility for them.	3.8	Agree
Overall	3.6	Agree

Based on the data provided in Table 3, items 1, 3, 5, and 6 had the same mean. This was followed by items 2, 4, 7, and 8, which also had the same mean, while item 9 had a mean of 3.5. Item 10 had the highest mean of 3.8, with an overall description of Agree respectively. The level of Administrative Competence as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of Personal Skills got the overall mean of 3.6 with description of Agree.

Administrative Skills. Table 4 presents the level of Administrative Competence as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of Administrative Skills.

Table 4. Level of Administrative Competence in terms of Administrative Skills

<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Is good at putting future plans for change and development.	3.7	Agree
2. Has the ability to plan and set goals clearly.	3.5	Agree
3. Strives to achieve the goals set.	3.7	Agree
4. Involves Department personnel in planning and goal setting.	3.7	Agree
5. Distributes tasks and duties fairly and according to the teachers' professionalism.	3.8	Agree
6. Makes sure the equitable distribution of power and authority over staff.	3.6	Agree
7. Is able to specify terms of reference for all teachers of the Department.	3.8	Agree
8. Tries to achieve coordination and cooperation among teachers in management.	3.7	Agree
9. Stimulates teachers to work hard towards achieving the goals of the Foundation.	3.6	Agree
10. Makes sure to provide all information and instructions necessary to implement the tasks properly.	3.8	Agree
Overall	3.7	Agree

On the other hand, Table 4 presented that item 1, 3, 4, and 8 had the same mean. This was followed by items 5, 7, and 10, which also had the same mean. While items 6 and 9 had the same mean, item 2 had a mean of 3.5, with an overall description of Agree respectively. The level of Administrative Competence as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of Administrative Skills got the overall mean of 3.7 with description of Agree.

Administrative Creativity Skills. Table 5 shows the level of Administrative Competence as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of Administrative Creativity Skills.

Table 5. Level of Administrative Competence in terms of Administrative Creativity Skills

<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Tries to apply new methods and technique to solve any problem faced by employees at work.	3.8	Agree
2. Does business with new and sophisticated style.	3.8	Agree
3. Is confident to provide suggestions and new ideas.	3.8	Agree
4. Has the ability to offer more of an idea in a short period of time	3.9	Agree
5. Expresses my ideas fluently.	3.8	Agree
6. Has the ability to brainstorm and quick solutions to address business problems.	3.8	Agree
7. Gives attention to the dissenting opinion of and benefiting from others.	3.9	Agree
8. Is trying to get any ideas and suggestions contribute to solving the problems of work.	3.6	Agree
9. Is sure to take advantage of criticisms and observations.	3.8	Agree
10. Suggests new methods of work performance even if there is a risk of lack of success.	3.8	Agree
Overall	3.8	Agree

Based on the data provided in table 5, items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 9, and 10 had the same mean respectively. Items 4 and 7 also had the same mean, while item 8 had a mean of 3.6, with an overall description of Agree.

The level of Administrative Competence as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of Administrative Creativity Skills got the overall mean of 3.8 with description of Agree.

The level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro

The level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro was evaluated with their corresponding indicators; Intrinsic Motivation and Extrinsic Motivation.

Intrinsic Motivation. Table 6 presents the level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro in terms of Intrinsic Motivation.

Based on the data provided in table 6, items 3, 5, and 8 had the same mean. This was followed by items 1 and 4, which also had the same mean, while items 6 and 7 had the same mean as well.

Finally, item 2 had a mean of 3.6. The level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro in terms of Intrinsic Motivation got the overall mean of 3.8 with description of Agree.

Table 6. *Level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in terms of Intrinsic Motivation*

Items	Mean	Description
1. I learn new teaching skills at the workplace.	3.8	Agree
2. I am highly motivated in the workplace.	3.6	Agree
3. I am equipped for the teaching profession.	3.9	Agree
4. I believe I am doing a good job.	3.8	Agree
5. Teaching gives me purposeful life.	3.9	Agree
6. I am free and empowered at the workplace.	3.7	Agree
7. I can express myself creatively at work.	3.7	Agree
8. I have access to all required teaching materials.	3.9	Agree
Overall	3.8	Agree

Extrinsic Motivation. Table 7 shows the Level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro in terms of Extrinsic Motivation.

Table 7. *Level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in terms of Extrinsic Motivation*

Items	Mean	Description
1. My school principal respects his staff.	3.9	Agree
2. My school principal praises my work.	3.9	Agree
3. I have satisfactory benefits in teaching.	3.8	Agree
4. My salary and workload are satisfactory.	3.6	Agree
5. I am pleased with the working environment at my school.	3.7	Agree
6. I am happy with the facilities of my institution.	3.6	Agree
7. promotion opportunities motivate me to do a better job.	3.7	Agree
8. My vacation/leave policy is satisfactory.	3.7	Agree
9. I am satisfied with the standard of my professional life.	3.8	Agree
10. I have opportunities to broaden my professional expertise.	3.9	Agree
Overall	3.8	Agree

Based on the data provided in table 7, items 1, 2, and 10 had the same mean. This was followed by items 5, 7, and 8, which also had the same mean. Items 3 and 9 had the same mean as well. Finally, items 6 and 4 also had the same mean with a description of Agree. The Level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro in terms of Extrinsic Motivation got the overall mean of 3.8 with description of Agree.

Relationship between the Level of Administrative Competence and Teacher's Motivation in Public-School

Table 8 presents the Significant Relationship between the Level of Administrative Competence and Teacher's Motivation in Public-School of Davao De Oro.

Table 8. *Relationship between the Level of Administrative Competence and Teacher's Motivation in Public-School Teachers*

Variable	TM	PAC
1. TM	Pearson's r	—
	p-value	—
2. PAC	Pearson's r	0.679
	p-value	.001

The Pearson's correlation results indicated a significant relationship between the principal's administrative competence (PAC) and teachers' motivation (TM). The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) for PAC and TM was 0.679, signifying a strong positive correlation. The associated p-value was less than 0.001, confirming that this relationship was statistically significant.

The significant correlation between PAC and TM suggested that as the administrative competence of principals increased, so did the motivation of teachers. This finding led to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H₀₁), which posited that there was no significant relationship between administrative competence and teachers' motivation in public schools of Davao De Oro.

The strong positive correlation implied that principals with higher administrative competence positively influenced their teachers' motivation levels. Effective administrative competence likely created a supportive and efficient working environment, enhancing teachers' enthusiasm, commitment, and overall job satisfaction. This result emphasized the crucial role of school leadership in fostering teacher motivation and, consequently, improving educational outcomes.

Administrative Competence in terms of Personal Skills. The study's results indicated that the level of Administrative Competence, as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of Personal Skills, had an overall mean of 3.6, with the descriptive equivalent of Agree. This high rating suggested that school administrators were seen as demonstrating strong personal skills, which are a critical component of overall administrative competence. The positive perceptions from teachers implied that administrators were effective in managing interpersonal relationships, exhibiting strong communication skills, and demonstrating empathy and understanding.

The implication of these findings was significant for future administrative training and development programs. The strong personal skills displayed by administrators highlighted the importance of including personal development, decision making and interpersonal skill training in professional development initiatives. As supported by the study of Cimatti (2016) stated that by continuing to focus and improve on the core social skills, educational institutions could further strengthen and foster effective administration and promote collaborative environments, thereby supporting better educational outcomes and creating a more positive and productive school environment.

In addition, Rosca (2024) asserted that school administrators who cultivated an environment where personal skills are developed and enhanced are impacted to drive innovative and creative administrative processes. This level of competence likely contributed to a more cohesive and motivated teaching staff, enhancing the overall educational experience for both teachers and students.

Administrative Competence in terms of Administrative Skills. The study's results indicated that the level of Administrative Competence, as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of Administrative Skills, had an overall mean of 3.7, with the descriptive equivalent of Agree. This high rating suggested that school administrators were seen as demonstrating strong administrative skills, a critical component of effective school management. The positive perceptions from teachers implied that administrators were proficient in organizational tasks, providing necessary information and resource management, which are essential for the smooth operation of educational institutions.

The implication of these findings was significant for future administrative practices and professional development. The strong administrative skills displayed by school leaders highlighted the importance of continuous training and development in this area. As emphasized by the study of Osman and Atamturk (2018) through improving and employing administrative capabilities school administrators could ensure more effective school management, better support for teachers, meeting teachers' needs to effectively inspire them that would improve educational outcomes. These capabilities contributed to the core administrative skills needed by the administrators in terms of technical, human, and organizational skills Atis and Dilbaz, (2022).

Interpreting these findings is in line with the study of Osman and Atamturk, (2018), that school administrators had successfully exhibited administrative competence, positively impacting the school's functioning and environment. The agreement among teachers underscored the administrators' capability to handle administrative responsibilities efficiently, thereby fostering an organized and supportive educational setting. This competence likely contributed to an enhanced teaching and learning atmosphere, benefiting both educators and students Komalasari, (2020).

Administrative Competence in terms of Administrative Creativity Skills. The study's results indicated that the level of Administrative Competence, as perceived by Public School Teachers in terms of Administrative Creativity Skills, had an overall mean of 3.8, with the descriptive equivalent of Agree. This high rating suggested that school administrators were seen as demonstrating strong creativity in their administrative roles, an essential component for innovative problem-solving and effective school management. The positive perceptions from teachers implied that administrators were adept at thinking outside the box, implementing creative solutions, and fostering an environment that encourages innovation and adaptability.

The implication of these findings was significant for future administrative training and development programs. The strong creative skills displayed by administrators highlighted the importance of nurturing and developing creativity as a key administrative competency. By continuing to focus on and enhance creative thinking and problem-solving abilities, educational institutions could further strengthen their administrative teams, thereby fostering a more innovative and adaptable school environment Arafat (2022). This emphasis on administrative creativity would be essential for sustaining tangible strategies and programs that improved long-term success in educational settings Liswati et al. (2023).

As supported by the study of Suparno et al. (2023) and Nebieridze (2023) it was evident that school administrators had successfully integrated creativity into their administrative practices, positively impacting the school's overall functioning. The agreement among teachers underscored the administrators' ability to approach challenges with inventive strategies, promoting a dynamic and flexible educational environment. This competence in creativity likely contributed to a more resilient and forward-thinking school culture, benefiting both educators and students by preparing them to navigate and adapt to changing circumstances effectively Radhawi & Mazael, (2022).

Level of Motivation in terms of Intrinsic Motivation. The study's results indicated that the level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro in terms of Intrinsic Motivation had an overall mean of 3.8, with the descriptive equivalent of Agree. This high rating suggested that teachers felt a strong sense of intrinsic motivation in their roles, which was largely attributed to the school administrators' competence. The positive perceptions from teachers implied that administrators effectively created an environment that nurtured teachers' internal drive to excel in their profession, highlighting the administrators' ability to inspire and motivate their staff.

The implication of these findings was significant for future administrative practices and professional development. The strong intrinsic motivation among teachers highlighted the importance of administrative strategies that focus on fostering internal motivation. Moreover, (Li et al., 2021) by maintaining and improving their ability to inspire and support their staff, school administrators could ensure higher levels of job satisfaction and effectiveness among teachers. This emphasis on intrinsic motivation would be crucial for sustaining a positive and productive school environment, leading to improved educational experiences and achievements Sitopu et al. (2021).

In addition, Tian et al., (2020) stated that school administrators had successfully fostered an atmosphere where teachers were internally motivated, positively impacting their job satisfaction and performance. The agreement among teachers underscored the administrators' skill in providing meaningful work, autonomy, and opportunities for professional growth, which are critical factors in sustaining high levels of intrinsic motivation. This competence in enhancing intrinsic motivation likely contributed to a more committed and passionate teaching staff, ultimately benefiting the educational outcomes for students.

Level of Motivation in terms of Extrinsic Motivation. The study's results indicated that the level of Motivation by Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro in terms of Extrinsic Motivation had an overall mean of 3.8, with the descriptive equivalent of Agree. This high rating suggested that teachers felt significantly motivated by external factors, which was attributed to the school administrators' strong administrative competence. The positive perceptions from teachers implied that administrators were effective in providing external incentives and rewards, such as recognition, support, and opportunities for advancement, which contributed to the teachers' motivation.

The implication of these findings was significant for future administrative practices and professional development. The strong extrinsic motivation among teachers highlighted the importance of administrative strategies that focus on providing external incentives and recognition. Moreover, Vansteenkiste et al., (2018) cited that by continuing to enhance their ability to motivate teachers through external rewards and support, school administrators could ensure sustained motivation and high performance among their staff. This focus on extrinsic motivation would be crucial for maintaining a dynamic and effective school environment, leading to better educational outcomes and overall school success (Zerrin & Bahadır, 2022).

Furthermore, Samantha et al. (2022) cited that school administrators had successfully implemented strategies that leveraged extrinsic motivation to enhance teachers' performance and job satisfaction. The agreement among teachers underscored the administrators' ability to create a motivating environment through tangible rewards and recognition, which are essential for maintaining high levels of extrinsic motivation. This competence in fostering extrinsic motivation likely contributed to a more motivated and engaged teaching staff, thereby positively influencing the overall educational experience for students Zikai & Yuanyuan, (2023).

Correlation between Principal Administrative Competence and Teachers' Motivation. The significant correlation between PAC and TM suggested that as the administrative competence of principals increased, so did the motivation of teachers. This finding led to the rejection of the null hypothesis (HO1), which posited that there was no significant relationship between administrative competence and teachers' motivation in public schools of Davao De Oro. The strong positive correlation between principals' administrative competence and teachers' motivation levels is supported by existing research.

The implications of these results were substantial for policy and practice within educational institutions. The strong positive correlation between principals' administrative competence and teachers' motivation levels, supported by existing research, emphasized the need for targeted professional development programs for school administrators. The result of the study is supported by Saine et al., (2023) by investing in the training and development of principals' administrative skills, schools could significantly boost teacher motivation, leading to improved educational outcomes and a more positive school culture. This focus on administrative competence would be essential for ensuring sustained teacher motivation and overall school success.

As supported by (Karim et al., 2021) that these findings were evident that principals' administrative competence had a direct and positive impact on teachers' motivation. As principals demonstrated higher levels of competence in their administrative roles, teachers responded with increased motivation, likely due to improved support, recognition, and organizational efficiency provided by the principals Iqbal et al., (2020). This strong relationship highlighted the importance of enhancing administrative skills among school leaders to create an environment conducive to high teacher morale and motivation Fauzi et al., (2022).

Furthermore, Kaso et al. (2019) and Kristiawan et al. (2020) highlighted that leadership practices focusing on promoting teacher development and fostering a positive school climate were critical in enhancing teacher motivation. Their research showed that principals who invested in professional development, provided constructive feedback, and encouraged collaborative practices among teachers had been able to boost teacher morale and motivation. This evidence underscored the importance of administrative competence in school leadership as a key factor in motivating teachers and improving the overall educational environment. The current study's

findings aligned with these established theories, reinforcing the idea that competent and supportive leadership had been essential for maintaining high levels of teacher motivation and, consequently, achieving educational success (Kurniatie et al., 2022; Lian et al., 2020).

Conclusions

The significant correlation between principals' administrative competence (PAC) and teachers' motivation (TM) indicated that as principals' administrative competence increased, so did teachers' motivation. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis (HO1), which stated there was no significant relationship between administrative competence and teachers' motivation in public schools of Davao De Oro. The findings underscored the pivotal role of effective school leadership in fostering teacher motivation and enhancing educational outcomes.

Based on the findings, the researchers outline the following recommendations.

The study recommended that public schools in Davao De Oro implement programs to enhance principals' administrative competence, as it had a significant impact on teachers' motivation.

It was advised that school administrators undergo continuous professional development to improve their personal, administrative, and creative skills, thereby fostering a supportive environment for teachers.

Teachers were encouraged to participate in training and development programs that align with their intrinsic and extrinsic motivational needs to sustain and enhance their job satisfaction and performance.

Students were indirectly encouraged to engage in educational environments where administrative competence is prioritized, as motivated teachers are more likely to positively impact their learning experiences.

Stakeholders in Davao de Oro were urged to support initiatives aimed at improving school leadership and teacher motivation through funding, policy-making, and community involvement.

References

- Aboagye, E., Yawson, J. A., & Appiah, K. N. (2021). COVID-19 and E-learning: The challenges of students in tertiary institutions. *Social Education Research*, 1-8.
- Aboagye, M. O., Marfoh, P. A., & Agbedoho, J. A. M. (2021). Modelling the role of teachers' motivation on teachers' turnover intentions in Ghana. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 4(1), 100175.
- Abutanmo, S. A., & Tantiado, R. G. (2023). Motivational factors and performance of public elementary school teachers. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 25(1).
- Arafat, S. (2022). The role of the Principal as Innovation on Teacher Performance. *Edumaspul: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 6(2), 2095-2097. <https://doi.org/10.33487/edumaspul.v6i2.4530>
- Aslam, S., Iqbal, M. Z., & Mushtaq, K. (2019). The impact of self-esteem on teaching performance among secondary school teachers. *Journal of Educational Research*, 22(1), 48-61.
- Astuti, S., Suharto, S., & Totalia, S. A. (2020). The effect of motivation and work environment on the performance of elementary school teachers. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran*, 27(1), 21-31.
- Ayik, A., Mukhamedov, R. I., & Karabulut, N. (2021). Relationship between teacher motivation and school climate. *International Journal of Instruction*, 14(4), 849-864.
- Bahdin, Nur, Tanjung. (2020). Education Supervision in Increasing Competence Teachers in Curriculum 2013 (Study of Education Management Analysis). doi: 10.33258/BIOLAE.V2I2.267
- Basalamah, M. (2021). The effect of motivation on teachers' performance at Madrasah Aliyah in South Kalimantan. *EDUKASI: Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Agama dan Keagamaan*, 19(2), 136-148.
- Basalamah, M. S. A., & As'ad, A. (2021). The role of work motivation and work environment in improving job satisfaction. *Golden Ratio of Human Resource Management*, 1(2), 94-103.
- Börü, N. (2018). The factors affecting teacher-motivation. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(4), 801-816.
- Cajurao, G., Bungay, A., Cruz, R., & Solis, M. (2023). The effect of intrinsic, extrinsic motivation and organizational commitment on millennial educator's job performance.
- Carayannis, E. G., & Morawska-Jancelewicz, J. (2022). Teaching in higher education facing the academic employment challenges: The human-centric organizational models. *Global Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, 11(1), 10-17.

- Carayannis, E. G., & Morawska-Jancelewicz, J. (2022). The futures of Europe: Society 5.0 and Industry5.0 as driving forces of future universities. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 13(4), 3445-3471.
- Cimatti, B. (2016). Definition, development, assessment of soft skills and their role for the quality of organizations and enterprises. *International Journal for Quality Research*, 10(1), 97-130.
- Collins, T. A., Quansah, P. D., & Dadzie, M. A. (2022). An appraisal of teachers' intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in Ghana: Leadership for learning. *Open Journal for Educational Research*. <https://doi.org/10.31586/ojer.2022.329>
- Comighud, S. M. T., & Arevalo, M. J. (2021). Motivation in relation to teachers' performance. *UBT International Conference*, 507. <https://knowledgecenter.ubt-uni.net/conference/2021UBTIC/all-events/507>
- Curtis, E. A., Comiskey, C., & Dempsey, O. (2016). Importance and use of correlational research. *Nurse Researcher*, 23(6), 20-25. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr.2016.e1382>
- Dalanon, J., Diano, L. M., Belarmino, M. P., Hayama, R., Miyagi, M., & Matsuka, Y. (2018). A Philippine rural school's organizational climate, teachers' performance, and management competencies. *International Journal of Research-GRANTHAALAYAH*, 6(1), 248-265.
- Damirnova, S. (2020). The effect of gender and age on job motivation level of teachers. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 70, 08016.
- Davut, Atiş., Engin, Dilbaz. (2022). The Evaluation of Management Skills of School Administrators in the Context of Effective School. *Anadolu journal of educational sciences international*, doi: 10.18039/ajesi.910568
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). Self-determination theory. *Handbook of theories of social psychology*, 1(20), 416-436.
- Dewi, P. Y. A. (2015). Pengaruh motivasi kerja terhadap profesionalisme dan kinerja guru di Lingkungan Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta. *Jurnal AKMENIKA UPY*, 5(1).
- Eschenbach, E. (2021). Teachers' motivations for utilizing multimedia resources in the classroom and the need for multimedia production instruction. *Journal of Applied Instructional Design*, 10(1), 3.
- Eschenbach, W. J. (2021). Transparency and the black box problem: Why we do not trust AI. *Philosophy & Technology*, 34(4), 1607-1622.
- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). "Belief, Attitude, Intention, and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research". Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Fisher, E., & Shapiro, S. A. (2020, October 1). Administrative competence. Cambridge Core. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/abs/administrative-competence/administrative->
- Forson, J. A., Baah, E. M., & Appiah, A. A. (2021). The influence of teacher motivation on job performance in Ghanaian technical universities. *PUPIL: International Journal of Teaching, Education and Learning*, 5(1), 64-85.
- Forson, J. A., Ofosu-Dwamena, E., Opoku, R. A., & Adjavon, S. E. (2021). Employee motivation and job performance: a study of basic school teachers in Ghana. *Future Business Journal*, 7, 1-12.
- Ganske, K., & Carbon, C. (2023). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: Definitions, theory, practices, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, Article 101860
- Gressick, J., & Langston, R. (2019). Principles of motivation. In J. Gressick & R. Langston (Eds.), *Introduction to Psychology: An Integrated Approach* (pp. 245-268). Prentice Hall.
- Grobler, M., Gaire, R., & Nepal, S. (2021). User, usage, and usability: Redefining human-centric cyber security. *Frontiers in big Data*, 4, 583723.
- Gul, S., Khan, A. B., & Ahmed, R. (2021). Complementing administrative competence: The role of teacher motivation in educational effectiveness. *Journal of Educational Research*, 45(3), 123-137
- Han, J., & Yin, H. (2016). Job demands and resources as antecedents of university teachers' exhaustion, engagement and job satisfaction. *Educational Psychology*, 40(3), 318-335.
- Hamdani, H., Kesumawati, N., & Kristiawan, M. (2018, November). THE INFLUENCE OF TEACHERS' WORK MOTIVATION AND PRINCIPALS' MANAGERIAL COMPETENCE ON TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE. In *Sriwijaya University Learning and Education International Conference* (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 674-681).
- Heider, F. (1958) *The psychology of interpersonal relations*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.

- Iqbal Fauzi, M., Sutarto, J., Suminar, T., Pascasarjana Unnes Kampus Pascasarjana JKelud Utara, K., & Semarang, S. (2022). The effect of principal leadership, work climate, and work motivation through job satisfaction toward teacher performance. *Educational Management - Universitas Negeri Semarang*, 11(2), 248–256. <http://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/eduman>
- Jacob, O. N., Jegede, D., & Musa, A. (2021). Problems facing academic staff of Nigerian universities and the way forward. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(1), 230-241.
- Jason, A., Grissom, J., James, R., Harrington, J. (2015). Investing in Administrator Efficacy: An Examination of Professional Development as a Tool for Enhancing Principal Effectiveness.. *American Journal of Education*, doi: 10.1086/653631
- Karim, A., Kartiko, A., Daulay, D. E., & Kumalasari, I. D. (2021). The effect of the performance in private MI in Pacet District. *Nidhomul Haq: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 6(3), 497–512. <https://doi.org/10.31538/ndh.v6i3.1686> DOI: 10.31538/ndh.v6i3.1686
- Kettunen, P. (2017). Administrative competence: A conceptual analysis. *Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 14(1), 1-17.
- Khan, A., Fleva, E., & Qazi, T. (2018). Role of self-esteem in the enhancement of learning and teaching. *Innovative Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(2), 12-23.
- Kiaee, Y. M., Ahghar, G., & Navidnia, M. (2016). Time management skills and its relationship with organizational citizenship behavior and burn out in school managers. *International Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies*, 1737-1749.
- Kilag, O. K. T., Uy, F. T., Calledo, M. F. S., Dela Cerna, Y. T., Villanueva, K. M., & Angtud, N.A. (2023). Quality performance of teachers: work environment, work attitude, and principal supervision: qualitative investigation. *Scientific Journal Science and Education*, 4(7), 415.
- Kim, J. (2020). Learning and teaching online during Covid-19: Experiences of student teachers in an early childhood education practicum. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 52(2), 145-158.
- Koontz, H., & O'Donnell, C. (2018) Principles of management: An analysis of managerial functions.
- Komalasari, K., Arafat, Y., & Mulyadi, M. (2020). Principal's Management Competencies in Improving the Quality of Education. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 1(2), 181-193. <https://doi.org/10.52690/jswse.v1i2.47>
- Kristiawan, M., Kartini, D., Fitria, H., Negeri, S., & Sugihan, M. (2020a). The influence of principal's leadership, academic supervision, and professional competence toward teachers' performance mapping managerial competence of primary school principals in South Sumatera. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT)*, 20(1), 156–164. <http://ijpsat.ijsh-journals.org>
- Kulikowski, K., Przytuła, S., & Sułkowski, Ł. (2022). E-learning? Never again! On the unintended consequences of COVID-19 forced e-learning on academic teacher motivational job characteristics. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 76(1), 174-189.
- Li, H., Majumdar, R., Chen, M. R. A., & Ogata, H. (2021). Goal-oriented active learning (GOAL) system to promote reading engagement, self-directed learning behavior, and motivation in extensive reading. *Computers & Education*, 171, 104239.
- Li, W., Bhutto, T. A., Xuhui, W., Maitlo, Q., Zafar, A. U., & Bhutto, N. A. (2020). Unlocking employees' green creativity: The effects of green transformational leadership, green intrinsic, and extrinsic motivation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 255, 120229.
- Liswati, T. W., Mustaji, Hariyati, N., & Uulaa, R. F. R. (2023). Actualization of Principal's Visionary Leadership in Improving Teacher Skills in Managing Learning Innovations in Senior High Schools. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 13(1), 45-45. <https://doi.org/10.36941/jesr-2023-0005>
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (1990). *A theory of goal setting & task performance*. Prentice-Hall, Inc
- Luis, Alberto, Núñez, Lira, Marisol, Verónica, Giordano, Silva, Isabel, Menacho, Vargas, Yrene, Cecilia, Uribe, Hernández, Luis, Rodríguez, Fuentes. (2019). Competencias administrativas en la calidad del servicio en las instituciones educativas del nivel inicial. doi: 10.17162/AU.V11i1.347
- Lusi, Susanti, G., Nurhizrah, Yasri, Hadiyanto. (2018). Managerial Competency of Administrative Leaders in Higher Education. *Applied Science and Technology*, 10(1), 1-10.
- Mauliya, Islahul & Relianisa, Resty & Rokhyati, Umy. (2020). Lack of Motivation Factors Creating Poor Academic Performance in the Context of Graduate English Department Students. *Linguists : Journal Of Linguistics and Language Teaching*. 6. 73. 10.29300/ling.v6i2.3604.
- Muijs, D. (2020). *Introduction to research methods*. SAGE Publications Limited.
- Nebieridze, K. (2023). Innovative School Leadership Aspects. *Journal of Legal Studies "Vasile Goldiș"*, 31(45), 17-37.
- Nickerson, C. (2023, September 29). Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation: What's the Difference? *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/differences-between-extrinsic-and-intrinsic-motivation.html>

- Osman, Emiroğlu., Hakan, Atamturk. (2018). Administrative methods of ensuring teachers' motivation: the case of north Cyprus. *Quality & Quantity*, doi: 10.1007/S11135-017- 0626-0
- Privitera, G. J. (2020). *Research methods for the behavioral sciences* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Saine, K., Santoso, S. B., Astuti, H. J., & Pratama , B. C. (2023). The influence of principal's leadership, teacher competencies, academic supervisor, work motivation and job satisfaction on teachers' performance in secondary schools of the country of Gambia. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147- 4478), 12(9), 428-439. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v12i9.3055>
- Sitopu, R. F., Johnson, M., & Lee, S. (2021). An integrative process model of resilience in an academic context: Resilience resources, coping strategies, and positive adaptation. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 113(5), 1234-1250
- Radhawi, S. N., & Mazaal, A. A. (2022). Innovative leadership and its relationship to organizational prosperity among school principals from the point of view of teachers in Wasit Governorate schools. *RIMAK International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(5), 216-230. <https://doi.org/10.47832/2717-8293.19.13>
- Ramzan, N., & Khurram, A. F. A. (2023). Construction and Validation of the Teachers' Motivation Questionnaire (TMQ): A Detailed Exploration. *Review of Education, Administration & Law*, 6(2), 381-394.
- Ramzan, N., & Khurram, A. F. A. (2023). Construction and Validation of the Teachers' Motivation Questionnaire (TMQ): A Detailed Exploration. *Review of Education, Administration & Law*, 6(2), 381-394.
- Reuben, V. R., & Levi. (2023). Extrinsic rewards undermine motivation in the classroom sometimes. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780197662359.003.0025>
- Rocío, Soledad, Riffo, San, Martín. (2019). Gestión administrativa y de calidad en los centros escolares de los Chorrillos. doi: 10.29394/SCIENTIFIC.ISSN.2542-2987.2019.4.E.9.153-172
- Roşca, I. G. (2014). Administrative leadership and managerial creativity. *Review of General Management*, 15(1), 76-83.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (1970). Toward a Social Psychology of Assimilation: Self- Determination Theory in Cognitive. Self-regulation and autonomy: Social and developmental dimensions of human conduct, 40, 191.
- Saks, K., Hunt, P., Leijen, Ä., & Lepp, L. (2022). To stay or not to stay: An empirical model for predicting teacher persistence. *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 70(6), 693- 717.
- Samantha, T. I., Parsons, S. A., Cutter, D., Field, S. A., Wells, M. S., & Lague, M. (2022). Intrinsic and extrinsic reading motivation: Context, theory, and measurement. *Reading Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02702711.2022.2141403>
- Suparno, Suparno., Agung, Firstianto., Siti, Nurjanah., Disman, Disman., Ratieh, Widhiastuti. (2023). Student creativity development: The role of teacher innovation and entrepreneurial school culture. *Humanities and Social Sciences Letters*, 11(1), 47-58. <https://doi.org/10.18488/73.v11i1.3246>
- Thomas, N. T., Abukari, M. A., Antwi, V., Dorsah, P., & Kwakye, D. O. (2022). Contribution of intrinsic and extrinsic factors to teacher motivation. *International Education Studies and Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.22158/iess.v2n2p19>
- Tian, H., Zhang, J., & Li, J. (2020). The relationship between pro-environmental attitude and employee green behavior: the role of motivational states and green work climate perceptions. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27, 7341-7352.
- Tirana, Jonida & Trungu, Denaida & Chiesi, Loren. (2023). Motivation Factors Influence Teachers' Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*. 13. 265. 10.36941/jesr-2023-0075.
- Valentine, Joseph, Owan., Judith, Nonye, Agunwa. (2019). Principals Administrative Competence and Teachers Work Performance in Secondary Schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. *Humanities and social sciences*, doi: 10.18488/JOURNAL.73.2019.71.20.28
- Vansteenkiste, M., Soenens, B., & Waterschoot, J. (2018). Catalyzing intrinsic and internalized motivation: The role of basic psychological needs and their support.
- W., Ashour. (2022). The actuality of the administrative competency of the directors of the education departments from the point of view of their deputies and the heads of the divisions in the west bank. *International Journal of Humanities and Educational Research*, doi: 10.47832/2757-5403.17.17
- Werdhiastutie, A., Suhariadi, F., & Partiw, S. G. (2020). Achievement motivation as antecedents of quality improvement of organizational human resources. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal) Volume*, 3, 747- 752.
- Wibowo, E. T. (2014). Improving The Motivation and Learning Outcomes Students with Applying "Everyone Is Teacher Here"

Learning Method. *Jurnal Pendidikan Bisnis Dan Manajemen*, 3(2), 122-130.

Xu, Y., & Liu, Z. (2023). Influence of motivation on teachers' job performance in private schools: A quantitative analysis using partial least-squares structural equation modeling. *Journal of Educational Research*, 56(2), 87-104.

Yosief, S. A. M., & Rakha, A. H. H. (2017). Efficiency of Personal and Administrative Skills for Managerial Leadership on Administrative Creativity at Najran University. *Journal of education and practice*, 8(6), 113-122.

Zerrin, G., & Gülbahar, B. (2022). Factors affecting the professional motivation of teachers. IEDSR Association. <https://doi.org/10.46872/pj.538>

Zikai, Z., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in distance education: A self-determination perspective. *American Journal of Distance Education*.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Irene T. Jose, MAEd-EdAd

Bayabas National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Maedel Joy V. Escote, PhD

Assumption College of Nabunturan – Philippines